

SOCIAL SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF ECOTOURISM IN GREEN TRANSFORMATION

Jabbarov A.,

Nakhchivan State University
[ORCID-0000-0001-9777-3664](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9777-3664)

Zeynalov H.,

Nakhchivan State University
<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-3481-2249>

Aliyev R.

master student of Nakhchivan State University
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11199898>

Abstract

The processes of globalization and the sharpening of competition taking place in the world at the moment make it necessary to adopt the principles of sustainable development aimed at the future and to apply more progressive economic management models. A creative approach to the issues of green transformation is interesting from the point of view of solving the crisis faced by the society in order to ensure sustainable economic development in a time when resources are depleted and environmental problems are becoming more acute. This article discusses the importance of implementing the concept of sustainable tourism in solving green transformation issues.

Keywords: sustainable tourism; green transformation; environmental education; consumer culture

In the modern world, the level of development of the green economy is one of the factors that determine the competitiveness of the national economy. In this sense, the attention paid to the ecological situation and consumer culture (3) is one of the most urgent issues in the activities of individuals and communities. But unfortunately, when the issues of creating a global coalition with a specific goal for the green future of the planet are on the agenda, international cooperation and, or healthy competition for the sake of building a low-carbon, resource-efficient and socially inclusive economy, instead of being solved and reduced day by day, on the contrary, it becomes more acute. Especially in developed countries, in a time when people waste many times more material goods than the consumption norm, CO₂ emissions released into the atmosphere by weapons used during senseless global and regional conflicts are not taken into serious account at this time, various interpretations are being given to the concept of “green economy”. For the green transformation, it is relevant to give priority to alternatives in energy consumption from traditional ones, to create smart residential areas, and to apply machines and equipment based on modern technology in household and production.

A number of researchers point out in their approach that the “green economy” improves people's well-being and ensures social justice. In other words, it is the fairest decision here that those who create more carbon dioxide (CO₂) by achieving a “green economy” and thereby gain more material benefits, have the same rights as others who have not done so, but who suffer from waste like everyone else (6). In another approach, while studying the green economy within the framework of principles, goals and activities, special attention is paid to the following features:

- ensuring sustainable development and stimulating economic growth;

- promotion of green business and green technologies;
- transformation of natural resources into real resources for socio-economic development;
- increasing the role of green infrastructure.

It should be noted that it is useful to add conditions such as consumer culture and the responsibility of individuals and economic subjects for the transition to green transformation. During the implementation of the green transformation for the development of the green economy, the types of activities that change people's consumption habits and inculcate a more “green behavior” model in the society by covering areas such as alternative energy, ecologically clean transport and waste management gain relevance at this time. In this sense, it is also possible to recognize the green economy as an economy that provides a higher quality of life using green technologies within the ecological limits of the planet.

Based on all this, the green transformation:

- the unreality of the infinite expansion of the economic sphere in a limited living space;
- it can be noted that it is due to the fact that it is unrealistic to meet the ever-increasing needs in the conditions of limited resources.

The green economy, in general, the “green society” in which the green transformation is supposed to be applied, is a high-knowledge, high-tech sector (7). In this sense, the application of green technologies in society brings to the fore the formation and development of the tourism industry oriented to nature conservation. Thus, ecotourism and other types of “green tourism” allow people to be involved in tourism activities as friends of nature, and to educate everyone as a lifestyle element. From this point of view, it is possible to consider ecotourism not only as a special type of

tourism, but also as an organizational form of “green tourism industry”.

For the sustainable development of tourism, it should first be aimed at satisfying human needs and ensuring a healthy life (1). Thus, modern industrial production with waste requires high physical and mental endurance of people against the physical and psychological stress caused by the increase in labor intensity in various fields. Only healthy and rested people can cope with these requirements. For this purpose, active rest and free time organized in the recreation complex should be considered as a demand of all sections of the population, the difference in the level of per capita income, population mobility, the values or consumption habits preferred by different demographic groups should be considered.

The development of sustainable tourism is clearly visible in its integration with the ecological situation and the general economy. These three areas always complement each other, it is impossible to imagine them separately from each other. Even the weakening of one of these areas affects the condition of the other area as well. Thus, when natural tourism resources are used in a rational way, there is not only a threat of disruption of the ecosystem here, on the contrary, the tourism income obtained by their involvement in the economic cycle creates favorable opportunities for the protection of not only the ecological situation here, but also the natural, historical and cultural tourism resources (10).

The ecological importance of sustainable tourism activity is directly related to the active use of the environment and tourism resources. The development of sustainable tourism and the protection of natural resources are directly related to the management of human consumption. Therefore, it is necessary to evaluate the impact of tourism on the ecological situation in both negative and positive directions. With the development of tourism in the area, the people of the region more accurately assess the value of their resources and understand the need to protect them. That is why the resources that were not used until the arrival of tourists to the area and were destroyed spontaneously gained a new value with the development of tourism and are protected.

Another important function of ecotourism in the green transformation, in particular, is the formation of consumer culture in relation to nature, leading to rational behavior towards limited natural resources. This is directly explained by the essence of ecotourism. Recreation and restoration of human resources in the natural environment allows to connect it with tourism types such as recreation-health, ecological, cultural-educational, scientific expedition, education, sports, adventure, village, agriculture (9). The essence of the matter here is the comparison of the pleasure a person gets from being in contact with nature and the pleasure he gets from getting to know its charm, and the use of natural resources for other purposes. In other words, if a person has the habits of acquiring more than he needs in his consumption actions for the sake of paying for material well-being, he is face to face with nature and

enjoys its beauties during active tourism trips (for example, hiking in the mountains, spending the night in a camp, fishing, mushroom picking). , collecting herbs, spending the night in a village house with minimal facilities, etc.), he learns that he can earn recreation by being satisfied with the minimum he needs. Therefore, at a time when the importance of green transformation is increasing, one can think about how relevant such trips are for those who have not been on active recreational ecotourism trips at least once in their life. It is precisely in this that the role of ecotourism can be seen in eliminating the difference in consumer culture between the representatives of the middle and young generation, who approach the nature of environmental problems on the planet in different ways, and are not ambivalent about global climate change and environmental disasters.

Findings

Green transformation comes from the need for global protection of the resources of our planet in the era of modern economic and cultural development. Living better with less damage to nature, transitioning to more green energy causing less carbon emissions and being more careful with our daily consumption, in this regard, has become a demand that manifests itself in the concept of sustainable tourism. In this sense, the role of tourism, which has mass influence in terms of understanding the nature of green transformation, its application in social groups, age groups and government management structures, is important in this sense.

Resources:

1. Cherevichko T. Development of tourism in a green economy. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/razvitiye-turizma-v-usloviyah-zelenoy-ekonomiki>
2. Svetlana I. Mishulina. Green transformation of tourism enterprises business models. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369783106_Green_Transformation_of_Tourism_Enterprises_Business_Models
3. Svetlana I. Mishulina. Green transformation of consumer behavior model in tourism. https://www.academia.edu/92806083/Green_transformation_of_consumer_behavior_model_in_tourism?uc-sb-sw=5970885
4. Нездойминов С. Г. Туризм в условиях перехода к «зеленой» экономике. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/zelenyy-turizm-podhody-regionalnaya-otsenka-osobennosti-razvitiya>
5. Савинов Ю.А., Уткин А.А. Основные факторы развития «зеленого» туризма в мировой экономике. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/osnovnyefactory-razvitiya-zelenogo-turizma-v-mirovoy-ekonomike>
6. Зомонова Э. Понятие и принципы «зеленой» экономики. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/po-nyatie-i-printsipy-zelenoy-ekonomiki>
7. Шнайдер В.В. Роль зеленой экономики в достижении устойчивого развития. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/rol-zelenoy-ekonomiki-v-dostizhenii-ustoychivogo-razvitiya>

8. Гурьева Е.В. Особенности потребительских практик в сфере туризма. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/osobennosti-potrebitelskih-praktik-v-sfere-turizma>
9. Лысикова О. Экологический туризм: глобальные тренды и локальные модусы социальных изменений. <https://elib.bsu.by/handle/123456789/47924>
10. Cabbarov Ə.X. Turizmin iqtisadi əsasları. Dərs vəsaiti. Bakı-2015.ADPU-nəşriyyatı. <https://www.kitabxana.net/files/books/file/1511415584.pdf>